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Research Article

**THE ROLE OF NURSES IN CHRONIC DISEASE
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suliman¹**¹ Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal Hospital - National Guard - Dammam – Saudi Arabia² Primary health care - National Guard - Dammam – Saudi Arabia**Abstract:**

Nurses play a pivotal role in chronic disease management, offering a multifaceted approach encompassing patient education, lifestyle modification, medication management, and psychosocial support. Their involvement is crucial in improving patient outcomes, enhancing self-management capabilities, and reducing healthcare costs. This comprehensive role is evident across various healthcare settings and disease conditions, highlighting the indispensable contribution of nurses to chronic disease management.

Keywords: Nurses, Chronic disease, roles, responsibilities

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INTRODUCTION:

The epidemiology of chronic diseases has become a critical area of public health research, particularly as these conditions have emerged as the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in developed countries. Chronic diseases, often synonymous with noncommunicable diseases, reflect a significant shift from infectious diseases, which were once the primary health concerns in these populations. (1) This transition underscores the importance of understanding the risk factors and prevalence of chronic diseases, which include conditions such as cardiovascular disease and diabetes. (2) Chronic Disease Indicators (CDIs) were established to facilitate the retrieval of data related to chronic diseases and their risk factors, enabling public health professionals and policymakers to address these pressing health issues effectively. The revisions to the CDIs, conducted between 2011 and 2013, emphasized high-impact diseases that significantly affect public health. (3) Nurses play a pivotal role in chronic disease management, significantly impacting patient outcomes through various functions and responsibilities. Their expanded role includes managing chronic care, which is essential for addressing the complexities of chronic diseases in primary care settings. This evolution necessitates ongoing education and support to enable nurses to fulfill these enhanced responsibilities effectively. (4) One of the critical functions of nurses in this context is that of the nurse case manager. This role encompasses education, planning, and administration, ensuring that resources are utilized effectively within a disease management model. As chronic diseases become more prevalent, the need for such comprehensive management strategies becomes increasingly urgent. (5)

Nursing Care Models in Chronic Disease Management**- Case Management:**

Nurse case managers coordinate care and facilitate communication among multidisciplinary teams. This is vital for delivering comprehensive care to patients with chronic conditions, ensuring that patients receive extensive and continuous care tailored to their specific needs. This coordination is crucial in managing chronic diseases, where multiple healthcare professionals often interact with a single patient. By organizing patient care activities, nurse case managers help streamline communication and enhance the overall quality of care (6, 7) Beside that, Their responsibilities include coordinating patient care, which involves facilitating communication among healthcare providers and advocating for patients'

needs. One of the critical aspects of nursing case management is the expanded role of registered nurses (RNs) in primary care settings. This evolution allows RNs to take on greater responsibilities in managing chronic diseases, which is essential given the rising prevalence of such conditions in the population. By implementing initiatives that enhance the coordination of care, nurses can apply interventions that not only address medical needs but also promote patient self-management skills. (4) This empowerment is crucial, as it enables patients to take an active role in managing their health, which can lead to better health outcomes. Chronic disease management encompasses a range of nursing care practices tailored to patients with comorbid conditions. Nurses are tasked with delivering interventions that monitor patient responses, provide symptom relief, and support both emotional and biophysical needs during hospital admissions. (8) This holistic approach is vital, especially as patients with chronic illnesses often present with multiple health challenges that require careful management. Care planning is another essential component of the case management role. Developing individualized care plans that address the specific needs and goals of patients is fundamental to effective chronic disease management. Case managers conduct thorough assessments of patients' health status and evaluate the effectiveness of these care plans, ensuring that interventions remain relevant and effective over time.

- Telehealth and Remote Monitoring:

The role of nurses in the management of chronic diseases through telehealth and remote monitoring is increasingly vital, particularly as healthcare systems adapt to the growing prevalence of chronic conditions. Telehealth nursing enables nurses to provide care and education remotely, which is essential for managing chronic diseases effectively. This approach not only enhances patient access to care but also reduces the time and costs associated with traditional healthcare delivery methods. Remote monitoring is a key component of this telehealth framework, allowing nurses to track patients' health status from a distance. By utilizing technology to monitor vital signs and symptoms, nurses can facilitate timely interventions and personalized care for patients with chronic diseases. (9, 10) For instance, the implementation of remote patient monitoring (RPM) has shown to prompt clinical interventions in a significant percentage of patients, demonstrating its effectiveness in managing conditions such as congestive heart failure (CHF). (10) Telehealth interventions are specifically designed to improve remote patient monitoring by recognizing signs of deterioration and providing necessary health education. This proactive

approach is crucial for patients with chronic diseases, as it allows for early detection of potential health issues and supports ongoing management of their conditions. (11) The integration of clinical support and remote diagnostic tools further enhances the capabilities of telehealth, enabling care that was previously only possible in person to be delivered virtually. (9, 10) The WANDA system exemplifies the advancements in remote health monitoring, utilizing sensor technologies and wireless communications to enable real-time patient monitoring. This system not only facilitates continuous health data collection but also incorporates data analytics to optimize user tasks and predict adverse events, thereby enhancing the overall management of chronic diseases. (12) Moreover, real-time alerts generated through remote monitoring systems allow nurses to respond proactively to changes in patients' health status, ensuring timely clinical interventions. (13) This capability is particularly beneficial for newly diagnosed patients and those with long-term management issues, as it fosters a more engaged and responsive healthcare environment. (10)

- Patient Education and Empowerment:

Nurses play a pivotal role in the management of chronic diseases, particularly through patient education and empowerment. Their involvement is crucial in helping patients understand their health conditions and navigate the complexities of their care. By providing education, nurses enable patients to make informed decisions about their health, which is essential for effective self-management. This educational process not only imparts knowledge but also fosters a partnership between nurses and patients, enhancing the overall care experience. (14) The concept of patient empowerment is integral to chronic disease management. It encourages patients to take an active role in their health care decisions, which is vital for improving health outcomes. Empowered patients are more likely to engage in self-care practices and attend educational sessions, thereby enhancing their ability to manage their conditions effectively. (15) Nurses, particularly those in case management roles, serve as educators, planners, and administrators, ensuring that patients receive the necessary resources and support to manage their chronic diseases. (5) This multifaceted approach not only improves patient knowledge but also builds their confidence in managing their health. Furthermore, the development of patient self-management skills is a key aspect of nursing care in chronic disease management. Nurses facilitate the acquisition of these skills through structured education and support, which is essential for patients to manage their conditions effectively.

(4) Self-management support, which includes assistance in decision-making and health management, is critical for patients with chronic illnesses. It helps them navigate their care and enhances their engagement with health care providers. (16) Coordination of care is another vital function of nurses in chronic disease management. By organizing patient care activities and ensuring effective communication among all stakeholders, nurses enhance the continuity and quality of care. (4) This coordinated approach aligns with the principles of the Chronic Care Model, which emphasizes patient engagement and the integration of care. (6) Ultimately, the integration of patient-centered care practices further underscores the importance of nurses in chronic disease management. By prioritizing patients' preferences, needs, and values, nurses can tailor education and support to individual circumstances, thereby improving health outcomes and patient satisfaction.

Challenges and Barriers in Nursing Practice

Nursing practice in chronic disease management faces numerous challenges and barriers that significantly impact the quality of care provided to patients. One of the primary issues is the lack of counseling skills among nurses, which hinders their ability to offer effective self-management support to patients with chronic conditions. This deficiency is particularly pronounced in the context of elderly patients who often manage multiple chronic diseases and medications, highlighting a critical need for enhanced training in counseling and communication skills. Inter-professional communication is another significant barrier. Effective collaboration among healthcare professionals is essential for comprehensive chronic disease management; however, communication breakdowns can lead to fragmented care. Nurses often find themselves at a disadvantage, as they may not be fully informed about the everyday challenges faced by patients, which can impede their ability to provide adequate support. (17) This lack of communication not only affects the quality of care but also contributes to the overall inefficiency in managing chronic diseases. Resource limitations further exacerbate these challenges. Insufficient staffing and funding can restrict the ability of nursing practices to implement effective chronic disease management strategies. This is particularly evident in regions with an inadequate number of healthcare personnel, where patients may struggle to access necessary care. (18) The geographical barriers and economic constraints faced by patients can also limit their access to healthcare services, compounding the difficulties in managing chronic conditions.

effectively. In specific contexts, such as pediatric nephrology, the challenges are even more pronounced. Nurses caring for children with chronic kidney disease (CKD) encounter unique physiological and metabolic derangements that complicate management efforts. These complexities necessitate early recognition and intervention to prevent complications and promote optimal growth and development in affected children. (19) Overall, the interplay of lacking counseling skills, poor inter-professional communication, resource limitations, and specific challenges related to chronic conditions like CKD creates a multifaceted barrier to effective nursing practice in chronic disease management. Addressing these issues through targeted training, improved communication strategies, and resource allocation is essential for enhancing the quality of care and supporting patients in managing their chronic illnesses effectively.

Workload and Time Constraints

Nurses managing patients with chronic diseases face significant challenges related to workload and time constraints, which can adversely affect the quality of care they provide. Workload management strategies are essential in these settings to ensure that nurses can effectively balance their responsibilities while delivering high-quality care. The patient load, or the number of patients assigned to each nurse, directly influences their workload and the overall quality of care. A higher patient load can lead to increased stress and burnout, which are prevalent issues in nursing, particularly in chronic disease management. Time constraints further complicate the situation, as nurses often struggle to provide adequate attention to each patient due to limited time resources. This limitation can hinder their ability to engage in comprehensive chronic disease management, which requires coordinated care and patient education. (6, 20) The relationship between nurse staffing levels and workload is critical; insufficient staffing can exacerbate time constraints, leading to poorer health outcomes for patients. Research indicates that a higher nurse-to-patient ratio is associated with better patient outcomes, highlighting the importance of adequate staffing in managing chronic diseases effectively. (21) In summary, addressing workload and time constraints for nurses in chronic disease management requires a multifaceted approach that includes optimizing staffing levels, leveraging the NP role, utilizing telehealth, enhancing patient education, and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration.

CONCLUSION:

Nurses' expanded responsibilities, patient self-management, and care coordination are essential to

chronic disease management. Their contributions enhance health outcomes and guarantee that patients receive comprehensive chronic disease management treatment. Nurses coordinate care, educate patients, and develop personalized care plans to address chronic diseases. Nurse case managers enhance chronic disease outcomes by fostering patient self-management and healthcare-provider communication. The significance of nursing case management in managing chronic diseases will continue to grow as healthcare continues to develop, underscoring the necessity of ongoing support and education for nursing staff. Telehealth and remote monitoring enhance the management of chronic diseases, enabling nurses to provide personalized, effective, and timely care. Modifying this nursing practice enhances patient outcomes and assists the healthcare system in managing chronic diseases. To effectively manage chronic diseases, nurses must educate and empower patients to encourage self-management and collaboration.

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